

Heritability (broad sense) and genetic gain in rice.

Character	Cross ^a	Heritability (%)	Genetic gain (%)
Days-to-heading	1	93.5	12.2
	2	81.2	13.0
	3	92.0	12.0
Plant height	1	66.0	12.0
	2	38.0	5.0
	3	32.3	7.4
Effective tillers/plant	1	84.2	64.3
	2	87.5	80.4
	3	89.5	76.8
Panicle length	1	32.0	5.0
	2	43.0	6.0
	3	33.2	3.6
No. of filled grains per panicle	1	91.2	54.8
	2	90.5	58.7
	3	97.0	61.7
Straw weight	1	97.0	87.8
	2	90.4	100.0
	3	93.4	91.0
100-grain weight	1	89.0	28.0
	2	65.0	11.0
	3	76.4	13.5
Grain length	1	25.5	29.1
	2	79.6	10.0
	3	38.6	40.5
Yield/plant	1	90.3	86.9
	2	91.5	94.6
	3	98.5	87.4

^a 1 = Kanchi/Jayanti, 2 = Ratna/Jayanti, 3 = IET1136/Ratna.

gains and high heritability, indicating non-additive gene action. Similar gene action was observed in plant height of Kanchi/Jayanti and grain length of Ratna/Jayanti. □

NDR80, a semitall, nonlodging rice

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At NDUAT we developed NDR80, a semitall, nonlodging, stiff-strawed rice with 115-d maturity. It averages 100 cm tall and is resistant to most foliage diseases. This line has high yield potential and adaptability for irrigated cultivation in India (see table). It has long bold grains with white kernels and has yielded consistently more than check varieties and other new rices. Semitall height helps

Performance of NDR80 (IET7626) in 1982 and 1983 wet season in All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program trials in India.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)			CD 0.05
	NDR80	Ratna	Rasi	
	<i>1982</i>			
Aduthurai	5.4	2.5	2.6	0.8
Coimbatore	3.5	3.3	3.2	0.7
Hyderabad	5.8	5.4	5.1	1.1
Cuttack	2.5	1.2	1.6	0.8
Jeypore	5.4	4.3	4.9	1.4
Karimganj	4.2	3.2	3.6	0.7
Agartala	3.7	2.7	3.1	0.2
Faizabad	5.2	3.1	5.6	1.4
Varanasi	4.6	3.4	3.5	1.1
Patna	4.1	3.0	3.8	0.5
Pantnagar	6.2	3.3	3.5	1.1
Kapurthala	6.0	2.4	3.5	0.9
Gurdaspur	5.8	4.0	4.7	0.9
Kaul	5.6	3.5	4.0	0.7
Nawagaon	6.5	5.1	6.1	0.8
Mean	5.0	3.4	3.9	
Mean d to 50% flowering	91	91	37	
	<i>1983</i>			
	NDR80	Rasi	IR36	
Mannuthy	4.8	3.3	3.9	1.3
Pattambi	3.1	1.8	3.0	0.9
Aduthurai	5.8	4.4	5.2	0.4
Coimbatore	4.6	5.5	5.3	0.9
Pondichery	4.5	2.3	3.8	1.3
Cuttack	4.6	1.8	3.6	0.8
Chinsurah	3.7	1.8	3.1	1.0
Karimganj	3.3	2.2	3.1	0.4
Raipur	3.0	1.8	2.9	0.8
Rewa	4.1	2.5	4.0	0.3
Kanke	2.4	2.1	2.5	0.6
Faizabad	4.7	3.1	3.6	0.9
Varanasi	2.5	2.0	2.8	0.9
Pantnagar	4.1	3.4	2.8	1.1
Kaul	4.8	3.0	3.3	1.2
Banswara	5.9	3.9	5.3	1.2
Kota	4.9	3.0	4.7	1.0
Karjat	2.1	1.8	2.2	0.4
Nawagaon	4.6	3.9	4.6	1.2
Mean	4.1	2.8	3.7	

it compete with weeds at early growth stages. At demonstration plots in Uttar

Pradesh, farmers have chosen NDR80 because of high grain and straw yield. □

Yield evaluation of major indigenous rice varieties grown on Cuu Long Delta

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Much of the Cuu Long Delta still is planted to indigenous rice varieties that yield 1.5-4.5 t/ha. In 1982 and 1983 we surveyed yields of major indigenous rices grown in Cuu Long and Hau Giang Pro-

vinces. Crop-cut samples were from 10 m² plots and mean yields were recorded.

In 1982 in Cuu Long, we took 407 samples of 52 varieties (Table 1). Where rice grows in fresh water, Trang Chum yielded well in fields flooded 31-70 cm deep.

Nang Cho and Nang Trich performed better in 71-cm-deep water. In fields influenced by salinity intrusion (5-8 mo freshwater regime), Lua Phi and Trang Lun yielded best.